

The Assembly of Disk Galaxies: From Keck to JWST

Susan Kassin

Space Telescope Science Institute

Raymond Simons (Johns Hopkins), Ben Weiner (Steward),
Greg Snyder (STScI), DEEP2 & SIGMA Survey teams

image courtesy Ceverino, Primack, Dekel

Raymond Simons

5th year graduate student at Johns Hopkins University

*photo removed
for publication*

- SIGMA survey of galaxy kinematics at $z=2$
- mock IFU observations galaxy simulations

How are
disk
galaxies
formed?

$z \sim 2$ \longrightarrow $z = 0$

Aumer, Binney, & Schönrich 2016

How are disk galaxies formed?

Dynamical Theory:
Disks start off well-ordered and thin, and thicken over time

Cold-mode

Halo 2
 $z=1.37$

1.0 < T < 2.0 Gyr
0.6 < T < 1.0 Gyr
0.3 < T < 0.6 Gyr
T < 0.3 Gyr

Stewart et al. 2013

How are disk galaxies formed?

Simulations: Gas & stars accrete onto galaxies directly from cosmic web; disks form early and outer parts added later

- high sigma caused by feedback (Ceverino et al. 2016), clumps (e.g, Bournaud et al. 2009, 14, Inoue et al. 2016, Ceverino et al. 2015, Krumholtz & Burkhardt 2016),

Observations: Disk galaxies are already in place at a redshift of 2

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THE KMOS^{3D} SURVEY: DESIGN, FIRST RESULTS, AND THE EVOLUTION OF GALAXY KINEMATICS FROM $0.7 \leq z \leq 2.7^*$

E. WISNIOSKI¹, N. M. FÖRSTER SCHREIBER¹, S. WUYTS¹, E. WUYTS¹, K. BANDARA¹, D. WILMAN^{2,1}, R. GENZEL^{1,3,4}, R. BENDER^{1,2}, R. DAVIES¹, M. FOSSATI^{2,1}, P. LANG¹, J. T. MENDEL¹, A. BEIFIORI^{1,2}, G. BRAMMER⁵, J. CHAN¹, M. FABRICIUS¹, Y. FUDAMOTO¹, S. KULKARNI¹, J. KURK¹, D. LUTZ¹, E. J. NELSON⁶, I. MOMCHEVA⁶, D. ROSARIO¹, R. SAGLIA¹, S. SEITZ^{1,2}, L. J. TACCONI¹, AND P. G. VAN DOKKUM⁶

¹Max-Planck-Institut für extraterrestrische Physik (MPE), Giessenbachstr. 1, D-85748 Garching, Germany; emily@mpe.mpg.de

²Universitäts-Sternwarte, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität, Scheinerstrasse 1, D-81679 München, Germany

³Department of Physics, Le Conte Hall, University of California, Berkeley, CA 94720, USA

⁴Department of Astronomy, Hearst Field Annex, University of California, Berkeley, CA 94720, USA

⁵Space Telescope Science Institute, 3700 San Martin Drive, Baltimore, MD 21218, USA

⁶Department of Astronomy, Yale University, New Haven, CT 06511, USA

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ABSTRACT

We present the KMOS^{3D} survey, a new integral field survey of over 600 galaxies at $0.7 < z < 2.7$ using KMOS at the Very Large Telescope. The KMOS^{3D} survey utilizes synergies with multi-wavelength ground- and space-based surveys to trace the evolution of spatially resolved kinematics and star formation from a homogeneous sample over 5 Gyr of cosmic history. Targets, drawn from a mass-selected parent sample from the 3D-HST survey, cover the star formation–stellar mass (M_*) and rest-frame ($U - V$) – M_* planes uniformly. We describe the selection of targets, the observations, and the data reduction. In the first-year of data we detect H α emission in 191 $M_* = 3 \times 10^9 - 7 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$ galaxies at $z = 0.7 - 1.1$ and $z = 1.9 - 2.7$. In the current sample 83% of the resolved galaxies are rotation dominated, determined from a continuous velocity gradient and $v_{\text{rot}}/\sigma_0 > 1$, implying that the star-forming “main sequence” is primarily composed of rotating galaxies at both redshift regimes. When considering additional stricter criteria, the H α kinematic maps indicate that at least $\sim 70\%$ of the resolved galaxies are disk-like systems. Our high-quality KMOS data confirm the elevated velocity dispersions reported in previous integral field spectroscopy studies at $z \gtrsim 0.7$. For rotation-dominated disks, the average intrinsic velocity dispersion decreases by a factor of two from 50 km s⁻¹ at $z \sim 2.3$ to 25 km s⁻¹ at $z \sim 0.9$. Combined with existing results spanning $z \sim 0 - 3$, we show that disk velocity dispersions follow an evolution that is consistent with the dependence of velocity dispersion on gas fractions predicted by marginally stable disk theory.

Kinematic Studies of Star-Forming Galaxies

winburne University of Technology, P.O. Box 218, Hawthorn, VIC 3122, Australia

9, 2013)

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lar kinematic morphologies despite irregular photometric morphologies and
number of highly gas-rich discs. There has not yet been a review of this
, I will discuss the extensive kinematic surveys that have been done and the

physical models that have arisen for young galaxies at high-redshift.

NASA

DEEP2 & SIGMA Surveys

of Galaxy Kinematics

Kassin et al. 07, 12; Simons, Kassin et al. 15, 16

- star-forming galaxies; **no cuts on morphology**
- galaxy kinematics from emission lines
- spectra from:
 - DEEP2 Survey for $z < 1.2$ (Keck/DEIMOS)
 - SIGMA Survey for $z \sim 2$ (Keck/MOSFIRE)
- ~ 550 field galaxies to $z = 1.2$, 49 at $z \sim 2$
- Hubble imaging, slits aligned within 45° (Weiner et al. 2006)

V_{rot} dominated

Mixed

σ dominated

- Fit emission lines for V_{rot} and σ , taking into account seeing
- σ was first discovered by Weiner et al. 2006
- σ is a *gas* velocity dispersion
 - integrates over all velocity gradients beneath the seeing.
 - **quantifies the amount of disordered motions in galaxies** (Weiner et al. 06, Kassin et al. 2007, Covington et al. 2010, Kassin et al. 14)

"Disk Settling"

$$\log \sigma = 0.2 z + 1.36$$

Kassin et al.12
 Simons, Kassin et al. 2016 & 17
 σ trend see also Wisnioski et al. 15

"Disk Settling"

Abundance matched galaxy populations

- $V_{\text{rot}}/\sigma \sim 10$
local massive disks
like NGC 4388

- $V_{\text{rot}}/\sigma > 3$
analog of local low mass disks
- $V_{\text{rot}}/\sigma > 1$
rotation supported

Let's
define a
disk
galaxy

"Disk Settling"

Fraction of galaxies with $V_{\text{rot}}/\sigma > 1$ increases with time

Observations: Disk galaxies are already in place at a redshift of 2

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² Universitäts-Sternwarte, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität, Scheinerstrasse 1, D-81679 München, Germany

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We present the K at the Very Large based surveys to sample over 5 Gy Journal home > Archive > Letter > Full Text cover the star fo selection of target $M_* = 3 \times 10^9 - 7$ galaxies are rotati star-forming "mai additional stricter systems. Our high spectroscopy stud by a factor of two $z \sim 0-3$, we sho velocity dispersio

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Letter

Nature 442, 786-789 (17 August 2006) | doi:10.1038/nature05052; Received 25 April 2006 July 2006

The rapid formation of a large rotating disk galaxy three billion years after the Big Bang

R. Genzel^{1,2}, L. J. Tacconi¹, F. Eisenhauer¹, N. M. Förster Schreiber¹, A. Cimatti^{1,3}, E. Daddi⁴, N. Bouché¹, R. Davies¹, M. D. Lehnert¹, D. Lutz¹, Nesvadba¹, A. Verma¹, R. Abuter¹, K. Shapiro⁵, A. Sternberg⁶, A. Renz Kong⁸, N. Arimoto⁹ and M. Mignoli¹⁰

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The Dawes Review 1: Kinematic Studies of Star-Forming Galaxies Across Cosmic Time

Karl Glazebrook^{1,2}

¹Centre for Astrophysics and Supercomputing, Swinburne University of Technology, P.O. Box 218, Hawthorn, VIC 3122, Australia

²Email: kglazebrook@swin.edu.au

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Abstract

The last seven years have seen an explosion in the number of Integral Field galaxy surveys, obtaining resolved 2D spectroscopy, especially at high-redshift. These have taken advantage of the mature capabilities of 8–10 m class telescopes and the development of associated technology such as AO. Surveys have leveraged both high spectroscopic resolution enabling internal velocity measurements and high spatial resolution from AO techniques and sites with excellent natural seeing. For the first time, we have been able to glimpse the kinematic state of matter in young, assembling star-forming galaxies and learn detailed astrophysical information about the physical processes and compare their kinematic scaling relations with those in the local Universe. Observers have measured disc galaxy rotation, merger signatures, and turbulence-enhanced velocity dispersions of gas-rich discs. Theorists have interpreted kinematic signatures of galaxies in a variety of ways (rotation, merging, outflows, and feedback) and attempted to discuss evolution vs. theoretical models and relate it to the evolution in galaxy morphology. A key point that has emerged from this activity is that substantial fractions of high-redshift galaxies have regular kinematic morphologies despite irregular photometric morphologies and this is likely due to the presence of a large number of highly gas-rich discs. There has not yet been a review of this burgeoning topic. In this first Dawes review, I will discuss the extensive kinematic surveys that have been done and the physical models that have arisen for young galaxies at high-redshift.

Quantitatively,
we're all in
agreement...

But only
 ~30% of
 high mass
 galaxies at
 $z=2$ have
 $V/\sigma > 3$!

Would you call these disks?

Aumer, Binney, & Schönrich 2016

Dynamical Theory: Disks
always well ordered

No.

Halo 2
z=1.37

Stewart et al. 2013

Simulations: Disks just add mass
to outer parts. σ caused by
clumps (e.g., Bournaud et al. 2009,
14) or feedback (Ceverino inc.
Kassin et al. 2016)

Maybe but parameter space of
physical processes in the models not
fully explored..

Use V_{rot} & σ evolution with z & M_*
as a *constraint* on physical processes
such as feedback.

We learn things when simulations
don't match observations.

- Mechanisms which may cause disk settling
 - decreasing **feedback** from star-formation (e.g., Krumholtz & Burkart 2016, Ceverino et al. 2016)
 - decreasing amount of **minor mergers** (e.g., Puech et al 2007)
 - **gravitational instabilities** (e.g, Inoue et al. 2016, Ceverino et al. 2015, Krumholtz & Burkart 2016)
 - **clumps** at high redshift (Bournaud et al. 09, 14)
- Unclear which are at play and when!
- Use these observations to *constrain* your models!

young stars
(age < 20 Myr)

VLT/KMOS ($H\alpha$)

**Major
mergers can
masquerade
as disks in
KMOS
observations**

VELA simulation (see Avishai Dekel's
talk Ceverino et al. 2014, 16)

Simons, Kassin, Snyder+ in prep

10 kpc

see also Hung et al. 2015, 16

young stars
(age < 20 Myr)

JWST/NIRSpec ($H\alpha$)

**JWST will do
for
kinematics
what Hubble
did for
morphology**

VELA simulation (see Avishai Dekel's
talk Ceverino et al. 2014, 16)

Simons, Kassin, Snyder+ in prep

10 kpc

see also Hung et al. 2015, 16

- likely reflects the [decline in SFR](#) (less feedback, minor/major mergers)
- higher mass galaxies arrive at an ordered state first ("[kinematic downsizing](#)")
- conclusions from high- z kinematic surveys depend on [sample selections for mass and morphology](#)
- powerful [constraint](#) for simulations